

Application of Functional Group Contribution Methods for the Correlation of Thermodynamic Parameters of Mixing for the Binary Series Cyclohexane – n-Alkane

R. PRATAP SINGH* and KUMARI SUNITA

Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur College of Engineering, Bhagalpur-813 210

Manuscript received 30 May 1989, accepted 26 December 1989

Contributions towards enthalpies ΔH^M of mixing for the binary series cyclohexane+n-alkane were calculated by equations based on analytical solution of group as well as regular solution models and the deviations from the corresponding experimental values were accounted for by incorporating a correction term involving series constants only. The overall mean % rmsd (root mean square deviation) and % normalised deviations in $(\Delta H^M)_{\max}$ which represented the maximum in ΔH^M -composition curves were calculated using modified equations based on analytical solution of groups as well as regular solution models and compared. Also, free energy ΔG^M and entropy ΔS^M of mixing were calculated and the contribution of CH_2 group towards $(\Delta H^M)_{\max}$ was determined graphically for the binary series considered. Further, the variations of ΔH^M , ΔG^M and ΔS^M with composition were used to discuss the mixing process involved.

IN order to assess the variations in non-specific interactions in liquid mixtures, it is customary to compare a real solution with the corresponding hypothetical solution based on ideal mixing. Though several equations, namely Wilson¹, NRTL² (non-random two liquid), UNIQUAC³ (universal quasi chemical) and UNIFAC^{4,5} (universal functional group activity coefficient) besides ASOG⁶⁻⁸ (analytical solution of group) and RS^{9,10} (regular solution) have been used in the past for predicting activity coefficients of the individual components of such liquid mixtures, yet none of them could predict satisfactorily the mixture enthalpies except in isolated cases.

The ASOG and RS equations use relatively less number of parameters which may be estimated by the structural group contributions^{7,8,11} of the mixture components involved and thus are comparatively convenient in their application. Accordingly, it appears worthwhile to compare a real solution with the corresponding hypothetical solution based on ASOG and RS models and attempt correlations involving the consequent deviations.

In view of the above, the present paper deals with the contributions based on ASOG and RS models towards mixing enthalpies of the binary series cyclohexane+n-alkane. It also includes the derived free energy and entropy of mixing data as well as CH_2 group contributions towards enthalpies of mixing.

Theoretical: The thermodynamic parameters of mixing of a multicomponent homogeneous

liquid mixture can be given by the following well-known relations^{1,2},

$$\Delta H^M = -RT^2 \sum_i \left[X_i \frac{\delta}{\delta T} (\ln \gamma_i) \right]_{P,X} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta G^M = RT \left[\sum_i X_i \ln X_i + \sum_i X_i \ln \gamma_i \right] \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta S^M = \frac{1}{T} (\Delta H^M - \Delta G^M) \quad (3)$$

where ΔH^M , ΔG^M , ΔS^M are the enthalpy, free energy and entropy of mixing respectively at temperature T , γ_i is the activity coefficient of the i -th component and X is the mole fraction.

Applying ASOG model to a multicomponent homogeneous liquid mixture, γ_i can be obtained by equation (4)^{7,8},

$$\ln \gamma_i = \left[\ln \frac{\nu_i^{\text{FH}}}{\sum_j \nu_j^{\text{FH}} X_j} + 1 - \frac{\nu_i^{\text{FH}}}{\sum_j \nu_j^{\text{FH}} X_j} \right] + \left[\sum_k \nu_{ki} (\ln \Gamma_k - \ln \Gamma_k^{(i)}) \right] \quad (4)$$

where ν_j^{FH} is the number of atoms other than hydrogen atom in a molecule of component j , ν_{ki} is the number of atoms other than hydrogen atoms in group k in a molecule of component i . Also Γ_k is the group activity coefficient of group k and $\Gamma_k^{(i)}$ is the activity coefficient of group k in the pure component i such that

$$\ln \Gamma_k = - \ln \sum_i X_i \alpha_{ki} + 1 - \sum_{i,m} \frac{X_i \alpha_{ik}}{\sum_m X_m \alpha_{im}} \quad (5)$$

where α is the group interaction parameter with $\alpha_{kl} \neq \alpha_{lk}$ and χ the group fraction in a multicomponent liquid mixture. In equations (1)–(5), $i, j, \dots$, represent the mixture components and $k, l, m, \dots$, the groups. Further, X_1 and α_{kl} are given by equations (6) and (7)^{1,7,8},

$$X_1 = \frac{\sum_i X_i \nu_{ki}}{\sum_i X_i \sum_k \nu_{ki}} \quad (6)$$

$$\ln \alpha_{kl} = m_{kl} + \frac{n_{kl}}{T} \quad (7)$$

Here m_{kl} and n_{kl} are the group pair parameters characteristic of groups k and l and to a first approximation may be assumed to be independent of temperature T . In equations (1)–(6), Σ_i and Σ_k cover all components while $\Sigma_k, \Sigma_l, \Sigma_m$ cover all groups.

For a liquid mixture of the binary series cyclohexane (i)– n -alkane (j) with group k representing $-\text{CyCH}$ for cyclohexane as a whole and l representing $-\text{CH}_2-$ as the characteristic group for n -alkanes and also utilising equations (1), (4) and (5), we can write,

$$\Delta H^M = -R \left[X_i \left\{ \frac{\nu_{ki} X_i^2 \alpha_{kl}^2 n_{kl}}{(X_k + X_i \alpha_{kl})^2} + \frac{\nu_{kl} X_i^2 n_{lk} \alpha_{lk}}{(X_1 + X_k \alpha_{lk})^2} \right\} + X_j \left\{ \frac{\nu_{lj} X_j^2 \alpha_{lk}^2 n_{lk}}{(X_k + X_j \alpha_{lk})^2} + \frac{\nu_{jl} X_j^2 n_{kl} \alpha_{kl}}{(X_k + X_j \alpha_{kl})^2} \right\} \right] \quad (8)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \gamma_i = & \left[\ln \frac{\nu_i^{\text{FH}}}{\sum_j \nu_j^{\text{FH}} X_j} + 1 - \frac{\nu_i^{\text{FH}}}{\sum_j \nu_j^{\text{FH}} X_j} \right] \\ & + \nu_{kl} \left\{ -\ln (X_i \alpha_{kl} + X_k) + 1 \right. \\ & - \left. \left(\frac{X_i \alpha_{lk}}{X_1 + X_k \alpha_{lk}} + \frac{X_k}{X_1 \alpha_{kl} + X_k} \right) \right\} - \left\{ -\ln (X_i^{(i)} \alpha_{kl} + X_k^{(i)}) + 1 \right. \\ & - \left. \left(\frac{X_i^{(i)} \alpha_{lk}}{X_1^{(i)} + X_k^{(i)} \alpha_{lk}} + \frac{X_k^{(i)}}{X_1^{(i)} \alpha_{kl} + X_k^{(i)}} \right) \right\} + \nu_{ll} \left[\left\{ -\ln (X_i + X_k \alpha_{kl}) \right. \right. \\ & + 1 - \left. \left. \left(\frac{X_k \alpha_{kl}}{X_k + X_1 \alpha_{kl}} + \frac{X_1}{X_1 + X_k \alpha_{lk}} \right) \right\} - \left\{ -\ln (X_i^{(i)} + X_k^{(i)} \alpha_{lk}) + 1 \right. \right. \\ & - \left. \left. \left(\frac{X_k^{(i)} \alpha_{kl}}{X_k^{(i)} + X_1^{(i)} \alpha_{kl}} + \frac{X_1^{(i)}}{X_1^{(i)} + X_k^{(i)} \alpha_{lk}} \right) \right\} \right] \quad (9) \end{aligned}$$

An equation for $\ln \gamma_j$ similar to equation (9) can be obtained likewise. With the help of equations (2), (3), (8) and (9), the values of ΔG^M and ΔS^M can be obtained conveniently.

In case the RS model is applied, ΔH^M for the binary mixtures can be given by equation (10)¹⁰,

$$\Delta H^M = \frac{X_i X_j V_i V_j (\delta_i - \delta_j)^2}{X_i V_i + X_j V_j} \quad (10)$$

where δ_i and δ_j are the solubility parameters and V_i, V_j the molar volumes for the components i and j respectively.

Results and Discussion

According to ASOG model¹³, the homogeneous liquid mixtures for the binary series cyclohexane (i)– n -alkane (j) involve the interactions of $-\text{CyCH}$ group representing cyclohexane as a whole and $-\text{CH}_2-$ ($\sim-\text{CH}_2$) representing n -alkanes. The required literature values¹⁴ of ASOG model parameters $m_{kl}, m_{lk}, n_{kl}, n_{lk}$ are listed in Table 1 while the parameters $\nu_i^{\text{FH}}, \nu_j^{\text{FH}}, \nu_{kl}$, and ν_{lj} are listed in Table 2. These parametric values were found quite satisfactory for predicting the activity coefficients of the cyclohexane (i)– n -alkane (j) binaries by earlier workers^{6,13–16}. However, when the

TABLE 1—VALUES OF GROUP PAIR PARAMETERS OF THE GROUPS $-\text{CyCH}$ AND $-\text{CH}_2-$

k/l	$-\text{CyCH}$		$-\text{CH}_2-$	
	m	n	m	n
$-\text{CyCH}$	0	0	-0.184 25	0 306 24
$-\text{CH}_2-$	0.152 97	2.078 7	0	0

TABLE 2—VALUES OF $\nu_i^{\text{FH}}, \nu_j^{\text{FH}}, \nu_{kl}, \nu_{lj}$ AND δ FOR BINARY SERIES CYCLOHEXANE (i) + n -ALKANE (j)

Component (j)	$\nu_i^{\text{FH}}/\nu_{kl}$	$\nu_j^{\text{FH}}/\nu_{lj}$	δ (cal/CC) ^{1,12}		
			298.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K
Cyclohexane	6	—	8.20	8.10	7.96
Hexane	—	6	7.27	7.11	—
Heptane	—	7	7.38	7.29	7.19
Octane	—	8	7.48	7.39	—
Nonane	—	9	7.59	7.43	—
Decane	—	10	7.65	7.50	—
Undecane	—	11	7.67	—	—
Dodecane	—	12	7.71	—	—
Tridecane	—	13	7.75	—	—
Tetradecane	—	14	7.78	—	—
Pentadecane	—	15	7.79	—	—
Hexadecane	—	16	7.79	7.68	7.61

same parametric values were used as input in equation (8), the calculated ΔH^M values represented by ΔH_{ASOG}^M at 298.15 K for different compositions of cyclohexane (i)– n -alkane (j) binaries deviated considerably from the corresponding experimental values¹⁷ represented by ΔH_{expt}^M . An inspection of equation (8) reveals that such deviations may be caused most probably due to inadequacies in the values of the adjustable pair parameters m_{kl} and n_{kl} as well as m_{lk} and n_{lk} because equation (9) involving the values of the remaining adjustable parameters α_{kl} and α_{lk} as calculated by equation (7) using literature values of m_{kl}, n_{kl}, m_{lk} and n_{lk} gives quite satisfactory values of γ .

In order to calculate $\Delta H^M - X$ data using equation (10), the δ values of the binary components were calculated on the functional group contribution basis by using equation (11)¹¹,

$$\delta_i = \frac{\rho_i}{M_i} \sum F_k \quad (11)$$

where F_k is the group constant for group k in component i , ρ the density and M the molecular weight. Using F_k values from literature¹¹, the δ values as obtained by equation (11) are listed in Table 2. The needed ρ and M values were obtained from literature^{10,12}. The calculated ΔH^M values by equation (10) and represented by ΔH^M_{RS} deviated widely from the corresponding experimental values¹⁷ because the assumptions of random mixing in RS model is unrealistic for the binary series considered.

The deviations are accounted for by using a correction term dependent on the nature of the binary series in equation (8) as well as in equation (10). The equation incorporating such a correction term obtained empirically takes the following form,

$$\Delta H^M_{corr} = \Delta H^M_{cal} + \frac{X_i X_j [A + B(n_c - 1)]}{1 - \beta(X_i - X_j)} \quad (12)$$

where ΔH^M_{corr} is the corrected value of ΔH^M_{cal} , A and B are empirical constants for the binary series at a given T while β for the binary $i-j$ can be estimated by equation (13)²⁰,

$$\beta = \frac{2[(X_i)_{max} - (X_j)_{max}]}{1 + [(X_i)_{max} - (X_j)_{max}]^2} \quad (13)$$

where $(X)_{max}$ is the composition corresponding to the maxima in $\Delta H^M_{expt} - X$ plots. It may be pointed out here that the β values as calculated by equation (13) for the binaries of the series cyclohexane (i) + n-alkane (j) do not vary significantly at a given temperature. The average of the β values for the binary series at 298.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K were found to be 0.345, 0.385 and 0.296 respectively and the same were used as series constants like A and B in equation (12). The values of the series constants A and B for $\Delta H^M_{cal} = \Delta H^M_{ASOG}$ and $\Delta H^M_{cal} = \Delta H^M_{RS}$ as used in this work are listed in Table 3.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF EMPIRICAL CONSTANTS A AND B , $(\Delta H^M_1)_{max}$ AND K_H FOR BINARY SERIES CYCLOHEXANE (i) + n-ALKANE (j)

Parameters	Temp. (K)		
	298.15	313.15	323.15
A ASOG	273.0	436.4	620.0
RS	-253.2	-247.3	-69.1
B ASOG	123.0	95.6	65.0
RS	141.1	124.3	92.7
$(\Delta H^M_1)_{max}$ for			
(i) $(\Delta H^M_{expt})_{max}$	64.8	90.5	—
(ii) $(\Delta H^M_{corr})_{max}$ from ASOG model	52.9	85.6	—
(iii) $(\Delta H^M_{corr})_{max}$ from RS model	53.3	79.4	—
K_H for			
(i) $(\Delta H^M_{expt})_{max}$	28.8	21.9	—
(ii) $(\Delta H^M_{corr})_{max}$ from ASOG model	29.4	23.5	—
(iii) $(\Delta H^M_{corr})_{max}$ from RS model	29.6	23.1	—

The rmsd (root mean square deviations) for $\Delta H^M_{corr} - X - T$ data as calculated by equation (12) with $\Delta H^M_{cal} = \Delta H^M_{ASOG}$ as well as $\Delta H^M_{cal} = \Delta H^M_{RS}$ are listed in Table 4. An inspection of the mean rmsd values for ASOG as well as RS based modifications show that both of them give satisfactory and comparable results. Thus equation (12) can be safely used for interpolation of $\Delta H^M - X - T$ data.

When $\Delta H^M - X$ data as calculated by equation (12) and the corresponding $\Delta H^M_{expt} - X$ data as taken from literature¹⁷ are plotted, the curves obtained are of similar shape and sign with a maximum in each case. A representative plot at 298.15 K is shown in Fig. 1. The ΔH^M values corresponding to the maximum in $\Delta H^M - X$ curves represented by $(\Delta H^M)_{max}$ are listed in Tables 5 and 6. The

Fig. 1. Plots of ΔH^M vs X and ΔG^M vs X for the binary mixture of cyclohexane (i) + n-heptane (j): Δ (—) H^M_{expt} , (Δ) ΔH^M_{corr} for ASOG model, $(\square)$ ΔH^M_{corr} for RS model, $(\odot)$ ΔG^M .

TABLE 4—ROOT MEAN SQUARE DEVIATION (rmsd) OF ΔH_{corr}^M WITH $\Delta H_{\text{cal}}^M = \Delta H_{\text{ASOG}}^M$ AND $\Delta H_{\text{cal}}^M = \Delta H_{\text{RS}}^M$ FOR BINARY SERIES CYCLOHEXANE (i) + n-ALKANE (j)

Component (j)	rmsd of ΔH_{corr}^M with $\Delta H_{\text{cal}}^M = \Delta H_{\text{ASOG}}^M$			rmsd of ΔH_{corr}^M with $\Delta H_{\text{cal}}^M = \Delta H_{\text{RS}}^M$		
	298.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K	298.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K
	n-Hexane	0.121	0.128	—	0.035	0.093
n-Heptane	0.108	0.044	0.080	0.041	0.050	0.042
n-Octane	0.052	0.042	—	0.042	0.063	—
n-Nonane	0.020	0.109	—	0.032	0.055	—
n-Decane	0.015	0.064	—	0.029	0.059	—
n-Undecane	0.019	—	—	0.013	—	—
n-Dodecane	0.032	0.067	—	0.035	0.041	—
n-Tridecane	0.018	—	—	0.036	—	—
n-Tetradecane	0.031	—	—	0.030	—	—
n-Pentadecane	0.032	—	—	0.018	—	—
n-Hexadecane	0.058	0.074	0.041	0.040	0.061	—
Mean rmsd	0.046 0	0.076 0	0.060 5	0.032 0	0.060 3	0.033 0

TABLE 5—VALUES OF $(\Delta H^M)_{\text{max}}$, % NORM DEV $(\Delta H^M)_{\text{max}}$, $(\Delta G^M)_{\text{max}}$ AND $(\Delta S^M)_{\text{max}}$ FOR BINARY SERIES CYCLOHEXANE (i) + n-ALKANE (j) AT 298.15 K

Component (j)	$(\Delta H^M)_{\text{max}}$ J mol ⁻¹		% norm dev $(\Delta H^M)_{\text{max}}$		$(\Delta G^M)_{\text{max}}$ J mol ⁻¹	$(\Delta S^M)_{\text{max}}$ J mol ⁻¹	
	Expt.	Corrected ASOG	Corrected RS	Corrected ASOG			Corrected RS
	n-Hexane	222.5	209.0	224.0	6.1	1.1	-169.5
n-Heptane	246.0	228.0	240.0	7.3	2.4	-170.0	6.50
n-Octane	269.0	257.0	261.0	4.5	3.0	-171.0	6.58
n-Nonane	290.0	287.5	280.0	0.9	3.4	-173.0	6.80
n-Decane	315.0	315.0	306.0	0.0	2.9	-175.0	6.90
n-Undecane	340.0	346.0	341.0	1.8	0.3	-178.0	7.10
n-Dodecane	382.0	375.0	372.5	1.8	2.5	-182.5	7.49
n-Tridecane	402.5	405.0	402.0	0.7	0.1	-185.0	7.50
n-Tetradecane	435.0	436.0	438.0	0.2	0.7	-189.5	7.73
n-Pentadecane	480.0	467.0	473.0	2.7	8.7	-192.5	8.14
n-Hexadecane	522.0	497.0	510.0	4.8	2.3	-194.5	8.25

TABLE 6—VALUES OF $(\Delta H^M)_{\text{max}}$, % NORM DEV $(\Delta H^M)_{\text{max}}$, $(\Delta G^M)_{\text{max}}$ AND $(\Delta S^M)_{\text{max}}$ FOR BINARY SERIES CYCLOHEXANE (i) + n-ALKANE (j) AT 313.15 K

Component (j)	$(\Delta H^M)_{\text{max}}$ J mol ⁻¹		% norm dev $(\Delta H^M)_{\text{max}}$		$(\Delta G^M)_{\text{max}}$ J mol ⁻¹	$(\Delta S^M)_{\text{max}}$ J mol ⁻¹	
	Expt.	Corrected ASOG	Corrected RS	Corrected ASOG			Corrected RS
	n-Hexane	205.0	207.5	220.0	1.2	7.3	-178.0
n-Heptane	230.0	230.0	217.5	0.0	5.4	-178.5	6.32
n-Octane	252.5	252.0	232.5	0.2	7.9	-179.0	6.50
n-Nonane	257.5	273.5	260.0	6.4	1.0	-181.0	6.60
n-Decane	280.0	297.5	290.0	6.3	3.6	-184.0	6.85
n-Dodecane	325.0	342.0	338.0	5.2	4.0	-191.0	7.10
n-Hexadecane	440.0	438.0	451.0	0.5	2.5	-206.0	7.90

absolute deviation between calculated and experimental $(\Delta H^M)_{\text{max}}$ were normalised and norm % dev $(\Delta H^M)_{\text{max}}$ were calculated. An inspection of norm % dev $(\Delta H^M)_{\text{max}}$ values (Tables 5 and 6) clearly justifies the correlative ability of equation (12). The overall mean of norm % dev $(\Delta H^M)_{\text{max}}$ for ASOG and RS models are 2.8 and 2.5 respectively at 298.15 K while 2.8 and 4.5 respectively at 313.15 K.

In order to investigate the contribution of CH_2 group towards $(\Delta H^M)_{\text{max}}$, the values of the latter

were plotted against $(n_c - 1)$ where n_c represents the number of CH_2 group in n-alkane component of the binaries. The plots were satisfactorily linear at 298.15 K as well as at 313.15 K for which sufficient data were available, giving

$$(\Delta H^M)_{\text{max}} = (\Delta H_1^M)_{\text{max}} + K_H (n_c - 1) \quad (14)$$

where $(\Delta H_1^M)_{\text{max}}$ and K_H are constants. The $(\Delta H_1^M)_{\text{max}}$ represents the maximum heat of mixing for a hypothetical binary cyclohexane (i) + methane (j) whereas K_H represents the contribution of one CH_2 group towards $(\Delta H^M)_{\text{max}}$ in the binary series cyclo-

hexane (*i*) + n-alkane (*j*). The constants $(\Delta H_1^M)_{\max}$ and K_H at 298.15 K and 313.15 K as determined graphically by equation (14) and listed in Table 3, show that the values obtained using $(\Delta H_{\text{expt}}^M)_{\max} - (n_c - 1)$ data are fairly close to those obtained using $(\Delta H_{\text{corr}}^M)_{\max} - (n_c - 1)$ data.

Since equation (9) with the parametric values as listed in Table 1 gives satisfactory values of $\ln \gamma$, the same was used alongwith equation (2) for calculating $\Delta G^M - X$ data. The ΔG^M values as obtained were negative in each case. A typical $\Delta G^M - X$ curve is included in Fig. 1. Utilising $\Delta H_{\text{expt}}^M - X$ data taken from literature¹⁷ and the calculated $\Delta G^M - X$ data the corresponding $\Delta S^M - X$ values were then obtained using equation (3). The ΔS^M values so obtained were positive in each case. The +ve ΔH^M , +ve ΔS^M and -ve ΔG^M values indicate that the mixing of cyclohexane (*i*) and n-alkane (*j*) in the binaries studied most probably involve heat absorbing steps, namely breaking of *i-i* type molecular species, breaking of *j-j* network and unfolding of n-alkane chains which overweigh the heat evolving step involving the formation of *i-j* molecular species.

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